

ASPECTS OF CULTURAL TRANSFORMATION IN GIRISH KARNAD'S *NAGAMANDALA* AND DEEPA MEHTA'S *VIDESH- HEAVEN ON EARTH*

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Abstract

This study analyzes the text *Nagamandala* by the famous playwright, actor director of the twentieth century Girish Karnad and *Videsh-Heaven on Earth* movie by Deepa Mehta through various different aspects like the cultural transformation of how that happens in the play as well as in the movie will be taken care of. The struggle between the myth, reality and dream that the protagonist of both the works faces. The extensive study of both the female character helps us to know the way the females were exploited in their day to day life. Through the study the psychological shifts that the female characters had to face was vividly observed. This experiment found the liberty that a film gets when an adaptation of a play is done. The exploitation of the female in Indian contexts will be interrogated. The present study intends to the psychological instincts that happen due to the cultural and the social shift in the characters.

Keywords: Culture, Myth, Reality, Dream, Psycho-cultural, Struggle

Introduction

Human being has created literature it helps us to study analyse and scrutinize man as a complex being. Literature majorly comprise of four basic genres that is Poetry, Prose, Fiction and Drama. Drama being an audio-visual medium of expression which represent humans and its doings most effectively. In olden times, according to Bharata, in *Natyashastra* "when the peculiarities of life in a society are connected with certain gestures or when the actions of gods, and kings are represented on stage it is a dramatic play". The drama is the imitations of situations. It is a show because it is seen. The current literary scenario defines Drama as an important literary expression whose grounds are rooted deep in cultural beliefs, empiric mode of knowledge and traditional signs human ethics and emotions.

A play is often an orderly sequence of actions performed in specified places for known durations of time. However, one looks at it, and play and playing are two fundamentally performative. The first thing to realize when a reader sets out to read a dramatic text is that the words written are not designed to function in the

same way as the words in a novel or a poem. The words are designed to become to become a performance in our minds, as readers. Cinema appeared a little more than a century ago to develop into one of the most effective forms of expression that has made its impact on practically every field of theory and practice. Cinema's dictum of happy ending easily takes most of its viewers out of their boring everyday lives into a beautiful fantasy land of happiness and contentment.

Adaptation since long ago has been the center to the process of filmmaking since almost the beginning and could have well maintained its dominance into the cinema's till the second century. The term adaptation in itself states that getting into the skin of the work or getting into the fundamental idea that the written piece of work tries to present. One basic and an important issue that happens with the adaptation in contemporary theme is how much it can be changed from the actual text and fabric of the story keeping in mind the sublime idea of the play intact. Some changes that are inevitable are, the geographical changes, social structure, the time of work, etc.

The present research will be conducted on the psychoanalytical study of the main character that is Rani in Girish Karnad's play and Chand in Deepa Mehta's film regarding their past and present life exploring on how the cultural shifts faced by the characters becomes the psychological instinct for them. Girish Karnad is the most important dramatist of the contemporary Indian stage that has enriched the present entertainment world with talent as an actor, director, writer and a producer. Born on 19th May in Matheran, a small town near Bombay, his entire childhood was spent in a small village in Karnataka. Karnad is a well-known and a renowned playwright. When Karnad started his journey, his plays were highly influenced by the renaissance in Western literature. Karnad found a new approach of drawing historical and mythological sources to tackle contemporary themes and existentialist crisis of modern man through characters locked in psychological and philosophical conflicts. Few of his plays are Tughlaq (1964), Yayati (1961), Hayavandana (1971), Angumalige (1977), Hittina Hunja (1980), Nagmandala (1988), Tale Danda (1990) and Agni Mattu Male (1995).

Bearing an Indo-Canadian origin, Deepa Mehta, a foremost female director of the modern era was born in 1950 in Amritsar, a border city between India and Pakistan. She is also a screenwriter. She is well known for her Elements Trilogy, Fire (1996), Earth (1998), and water (2005). After graduating she started working for a production company that made documentary and educational films for the Indian Government. Mehta directed several English language films set in Canada. For example- The Republic of Love (2003) and Videsh- Heaven on Earth (2008) which talks about the domestic violence. Films that she made came out with a key informing about the Indian and Hindu culture, which she in her movie is seen compare these practices with a more "Westernized" philosophy. The study herebrings up the characters of the female lead role that is Chand and Rani. The things that they had to face in there day to day livings. The myths that is shown in the drama as well as in the film. How myths became a part of their life's and how that lead to the misery that they had to face in their life. Through this dissertation the past and the present life of both the character's will be projected.

Literature Review

Talwar, Urmil, Chakrabarty, Bandana. (2005) in 'Contemporary Indian Drama astride two tradition' explored how Nagamandala a play within the play creatively makes use of the Indic oral tradition in its dramatic structure. Myths, epics and folk forms have been used for introducing and eliminating cultural miseries such as caste, gender distinctions and religious fanaticism. Karnad endeavors to construct a link between the past and present be it myths from the epics, folk tales or historical events to eliminate social and cultural miseries and put forward a question to some of the values of the society.

Tandon, Neeru. (2006) in 'Perspectives and Challenges in Indian-English Drama' explored that the Nagamandala is a classic in all respects, Karnad's play explores the energy of folk tales, which, according to him, springs from the fact that although it seems to uphold traditional values, it is a powerful tool for questioning the people in the society. However, paradoxically she neither belonged to this world or that: her parental home or her husband's abode. For the woman, the home is said to be expression of her freedom: it is her domain.

Paul G.S. (2016), in 'Marrying myth and mystery' explored that Appanna is a metaphor of a man, his chauvinistic stance and towering dominance to the extend of suppressing a woman's individuality by seeking refuge in dreams, fairy tales and fantasies to escape the sordid or prince coming on horseback, Rani's flight to the imagination transports her to the seventh heaven where her parents wait for her. So much for her aversion to the institution of marriage. Critics shows her body as a site of "confinement, violence, regulation and communication of the victimized gender –self". In Indian myth, a miracle has been mandatory to establish the purity of a woman, while a man's mere word is taken for the truth whether it be Sita, Shakuntala or Rani in this instance.

'Cinematic Analysis of Deepa Mehta's Videsh-Heaven on Earth' explores that *Deepa Mehta's Videsh-Heaven on Earth* focuses on the fictional depiction of a poor, working-class, first generation Indian family, living in Brampton, Ontario, which provide a microcosm of the pressures and realities of everyday immigrant life affecting the family from within. The text represents the ancient Indian myth of the Sheesh Naag, the King Cobra, with the ability to shape-shift and transform into human form to raise awareness about the issue of cultural driven violence against women in South Asian Canadian communities, which is on the increase in Canadian immigrant communities. Mehta's interpretation of the myth is based on Nagamandala a popular play by Girish Karnad, a South Indian dramatist heavily influenced by ancient Indian mythology. The cultural transformation that is shown between all the characters is shown in the play and in the film. The film *Videsh- Heaven on Earth* aimed to showcase the much spiritual, chaste and superior 'East' in the comparison to materialistic and sexually degraded 'West' to a simplistic extreme level. This movie is an example of the wide range of the ideological generalizations regarding the existential conflicts between the two directions that is the East and West. It is just as frequent as the other forms of adaptation like the cinematic adaptations which found an easy way in the literature world.

Ridon, Manjeet (2015) in 'Myth and Patriarchy in Deepa Mehta's Heaven on Earth' explored that in *Videsh-Heaven on Earth* adapts Karnad's South Indian version of the myth to reflect the characteristics of a diasporic Sikh Punjabi community living in Canada, which is predominantly North Indian in terms of its

ancestral origin. Karnad's version of the cobra myth privileges a male representation of the world. Mehta's retelling of the cobra myth will demonstrate that South Asian patriarchy, in its diasporic and twenty-first century context, is critiqued through myth and raises important questions about it becoming part of a feminist discourse. In *Videsh- Heaven of Earth* the recalibration to a myth that is recoded according to a feminist discourse in order to raise awareness about the oppression of some women in diasporic societies and to promote wider understanding of the phenomenon of Sikh's transnational marriages within poor working- class communities.

The adaptation of myth is also empowering of women and their roles within the community: a woman can free herself from domestic violence and choose the life she wants. Chand disrupts a patriarchal family in an enunciation of the Indian cobra myth, illuminating a feminist struggle that can be pursued by audiences and in the process raises awareness about NRI marital abuse, as it affects men and women.

Methodology

After reading the text *Nagamandala* by Girish Karnad, we came across the movie which is directed by the Indo – Canadian director Deepa Mehta, who named the movie as *Videsh- Heaven on Earth*. The primary source was read a couple of times so that the character can become familiar in order to get a better clarity of the topic. The movie was watched a lot many times so that all the changes that is there in the play can be seen prominently. Research papers, blogs, journals were studied as well as collected to guide through the important aspects of the play as well as the movie.

Findings

4.1 Struggle between Dreams, Myth and Reality

4.1.1 Myth and Reality: Instinctual ingenuity is a psychological term which refers to the loneliness, frustration, patterns of behavior's, plans, conspiracy these elements will be projected by both the female character in the play and in the novel had to go through. About this M.K. Naik in *A History of Indian English Literature* provides a fascinating account of the origin and the making of *Naga-Mandala*:

These elements are the basic ones that both the characters in the play and in the film projects. Also, in this chapter the struggle between the myth and reality will be shown. The title of the play *Naga-Mandalas* suggests the importance of the myth regarding the Naga. Renowned scholar, Laxmi Lal in her book, *Myth and Me*, rightly states, 'the Indian is Myth-born and Myth-fed'. It is believed that married women who pour milks in the anthills where the cobra stays will help them to get over barrenness and unmarried girls to get good husbands. A ritual performed according to the rites set down in the sacred texts or even inadvertently could bring the same value and effect. Similarly, in the play Rani's action of unknowingly pouring the milk with the magical root given to her by Kurudawa upon the anthill, the abode of the cobra makes the whole difference. For Rani the Naga (myth) is more pleasing and satisfying than her husband Appanna (reality). The Naga follows the footmark of the mythical version where Naga in the real world is worshipped as god of life and creation and not as evil to be detested.

“Naga utilizes the myth of life and fertility inherent in his genetics to train Rani about sex, sleep (nid), food (ahara), and copulation (maithuna) which are common to man and animal. Naga is used as the phallic symbol executes as per his nature or swadharma and seduces Rani into sex”.

While explaining the nature of sex to Rani the Naga who was disguised in the form of her husband used to say:

“Frogs croaking in pelting rain, tortoises singing soundlessly in the dark, foxes, crabs, ants, rattlers, sharks, swallows- even the geese! The female begins to smell like wet earth. And stung by her smell, the king Cobra starts searching for his queen. the tiger bellows for his mate. When the flame-of- forest blossoms into a fountain of red and the earth cracks open at the touch ... within everything that sprouts, grows, stretches, creaks and blooms- everywhere, those who come together, cling, fall apart lazily! It is there and there and there, everywhere”. (Karnad, —*Naga-Mandalal* 45)

Since the beginning of the Indian patriarchy system, chastity is one of the most dominating but still one of the most alarming societal chain that has always confined women for decades. The concept of chastity is a morose concept for a woman to think about sex is evil and corrupt and the most important duty of a woman of life is to preserve their morality and chastity. Rani's husband Appanna decides her fate and keeps her locked in the house. According to Rani, she fantasizes a loveable and affectionate Appanna with whom she spends some happy time regularly. Actually, the person whom she thought to be her husband was Naga who has fallen in love with Rani after drinking the love potion that Rani threw in the anthill. Everything went on smoothly until Rani becomes pregnant with the child of Naga.

4.1.2 Dreams and Reality: The struggle between the dreams and reality are seen in the movie that Deepa Mehta had directed. Dreams play a very crucial part in the movie because it through dream Chands get to feel a little warmth and happy from her lonely and boring life. When Chand is aggrieved and upset and beaten brutally by her husband Rocky, she dreams that she is in the comfortable company of her parents then when she meets her parents, she they embraces her and tiers comes out of their eyes. She imagines that the stag with golden antlers comes to the door and he explains that he is the prince. Eventually when Chand was deprived of all the happiness that she deserves she was very sad and felt lonely. The love potion was at last consumed by the snake in which she threw the potion because after putting bit in the food and it turned out to be like a poison of red colour. This made her throw the potion in an anthill. Instantly the snake fell in love with Chand. Chand used to dream that Rocky will make him talk to her parents but every day she was disappointed by Rocky and was not allowed to talk to her parents. Since Chand was deprived of all the pleasures her dreams became her only mean of feeling good. The struggle between the dreams and the reality and myth is shown with the help of both the characters Rani and Chand.

4.2 Analysis of Psycho- cultural Shift

The cultural shift that is projected in the play and in the film is that in the play it's a South Indian family that Girish Karnard talks about whereas in the movie Deepa Mehta shows an Indo- Canadian Sikh family. The shift that is depicted in the play is that Appanna took Rani home while she attained the age of womanhood. Before that Rani stayed with her parents and was eagerly waiting. In the movie Chands parents saw that the family where her father was fixing the marriage was an NRI from Canada they thought that her in-laws were well settled.

According to Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic principles, the personality of a human being is built upon three parts that is the Id, Ego and Super Ego. Human behavior is controlled by the Id that is it consists of instincts of peripheral reality and cultural values which is called as pleasure principle. The ego perceives reality and reacts to it as the reality principle. The Super Ego, irrespective of the external reality and biological impulses comprises of the ideals, values and morals that urges the ego to lead an ideal life. In the play Nagamandala, Rani is afraid of her husband. She pictures her husband Appanna as the demon who always refuses to talk and takes the house as the castle in which Rani is locked up. She in her fantasies sees the appearance of a 'prince' who is there to rescue her. Her inner desires and thoughts are directly represented in dreams. Rani's dreams are her 'wish -fulfillments'. The transformation of the Naga from a cobra leads to the identity crisis to the character. Naga, in the disguise of Appanna, exploits Rani at sexual levels. After admitting his position that he was a naga in disguised as her husband his position in the married life of Appanna and Rani, he proceeds towards death and hence commits suicide.

Id, ego and super ego are the concept that Freud came up with which describes the working of brain system. These are particular systems of the brain which work together as to how we behave and how it acts accordingly. The impression was laid off by both the characters that are by Rani as well as Chand through the mystical concepts and through dreams. Before sending Rani to her husband's house her mother taught her few basic necessities that each and every girl are bound to know and follow wholeheartedly that is they are not allowed to touch other person other than their husbands. Whereas Chands mother said her that she should stay happily with each and every members of her family and should take care of her husband and also of her in-laws. It shows the way ego worked in the play as well as in the movie is depicted in an explicit manner.

4.3 Aspects of Cultural Transformation and Adaptation

Basically, Nagmandala is a play that is written by the famous actor playwright of the recent times that is Girish Karnard the play is further adapted as a famous mood of entertainment that is film. The film is made by the famous Indo- Canadian Director Deepa Mehta. The play is very nicely depicted in a film that is Videsh- Heaven on Earth. The cultural transformation that is shown between all the characters is shown in the play and in the film. The film Videsh- Heaven on Earth aimed to showcase the much spiritual, chaste and superior 'East' in the comparison to materialistic and sexually degraded 'West' to a simplistic extreme level. This movie is an example of the wide range of the ideological generalizations regarding the existential conflicts between the two directions that are the East and West.

Deepa Mehta as one of the representative directors of the South Asian Diaspora in one of her interviews with Richard Philips, commented that, "There are several conceptions that prevail in the west about India. There is firstly the spiritual India – place where you go and find nirvana. Secondly, there is the conception that India is entirely poverty stricken.... It is uncomfortable and difficult for some filmmakers to produce works that destroy these perceptions. India brings specially fixed images in many western minds, and the minute you start de-exoticising that. You deal with Indians as real people". ("Worlds Socialist Website")(Cinematic Analysis of Deepa Mehta's *Videsh-Heaven on Earth*)

In the play the marriage was also devoid of love and affection but in the play Rani was locked up in the house when her husband Appanna went out and was instructed by her husband that she is not allowed to talk to anybody when he is not present in the house but in the movie since Chand was married in a Western country that is Canada she was forced to adopt the culture of the country. She was forced to work in the detergent factory after she informed her in laws family that she is a graduate and she can do a better job rather than working in a detergent factory whereas in the movie we can see that Chand is beaten very brutally by her husband Rocky when her mother in law suddenly came to the hotel were, they planned to spent their honeymoon night. When her mother in law was there in the ground she screamed for help when Rocky came and had beaten her brutally that her face was filled with marks. Where as in the play Appanna always used to lock her in the house and then go out this was also a type of physical abuse that can be seen in the play.

In Indian mythology, a cobra is believed to be a creature that has the power to change forms and can even turn into a human being to avert arrest and influence another human being. Chand experiences Rocky at the two extremes- an abusive ruffian and a romantic amorist. Chand begins to accept this unpredictable nature of her husband Rocky without even realizing that it might be more than just a case of split personality. In an ironical state, she finally decides to leave this hell which was her in laws place which most of the Indian is on heaven on Earth (*Videsh*). The play is very nicely adapted into a film. In 2008, Deepa Mehta adapted Girish Karnad's *Nagamandala* into a film, *Heaven on Earth* which depicted the household brutality personated on a newly married immigrant woman in Canada.

Conclusion

Contemporary writing in English presents a strange conjunction between at least three different categories: language, society and cultural tradition. This is a journey astride two cultures and across two traditions, yet it is an ongoing journey where, hopefully the forms and structure will expand to accommodate cultural needs of today. For Girish Karnad, the reason for writing is just as important as the means of expression. Although he is preoccupied with tradition, history, mythology, and storytelling, he is not a romantic idealist. He draws inspiration from an Indian story, retold by a Western writer, to examine serious issues concerning identity and completeness. Further how Deepa Mehta showed the character of Chand will be elaborately shown and the hardships that she had to face in her marriage will also be projected. However, it is a rare occasion that a play is translated into a movie. We focus on the three aspects that is myth, reality and dreams basically. How

the female protagonist of the play as well as the movie experience these changes are shown extensively and how their life changes due to these three components are seen. Also, the nature through which they were treated by their husbands was shown differently in the movie and that in the play. Through this research we can see that the analysis of the both the female character are portrayed in two different manner. In the play Rani was locked in the house and was not allowed to go out or talk with anybody but it can be seen that in the movie Chand was forced to work in the detergent factory after being a graduate.

Lastly, one can deeply interconnect the pathetic life that the Indian women face. It is through dreams that both the characters can see some happiness in their life initially. It can be seen that throughout the world women's are exploited by the males in the society. From the film we can see that the advantage of women is not only taken by the Indian males but also by the Jamaican males. The characters of the play as well as the film can be related with the present-day conditions of women's in India. The aspect of exploitation of Women's in India can be taken up on a large scale and can be worked upon further on an extensive way keeping in mind the play and the film.

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